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UNIFIED CRITERIA OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY AND SAFETY OF SURGICAL METHODS FOR THE TREATMENT OF BENIGN PROSTATE HYPERPLASIA

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ABSTRACT

Unification of postoperative complications criteria of surgical modalities for the treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) based on the Clavien-Dindo classification. Efficacy and safety evaluation of different surgical modalities for the BPH treatment by systematizing postoperative complications. 150 patients with BPH were divided into three groups depending on the surgical modality of prostatic hyperplasia. Group 1 consisted of 60 (40%) patients who underwent open transvesical simple prostatectomy (OETA), Group 2 - 50 (33.3%) patients who underwent transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP), Group 3 - 40 (26.7%) patients underwent holmium laser enucleation of the prostate (HoLEP). The Clavien-Dindo classification was used to adapt the assessment of postoperative complications of BPH operative therapy. To use the Clavien-Dindo classification for an unbiased evaluation of surgical treatment quality and systematization of complications, it must first be adapted, taking into account the method specifics and the postoperative period. OETA is an effective method to treat BPH but is accompanied by a longer period of hospitalization compared to TURP and HoLEP, more severe complications, conclusively more often requiring additional interference. In terms of trauma, blood transfusions frequency, and the length of hospital stay, the results of TURP are comparable to those of HoLEP but are inferior in morbidity.

Keywords: BPH, complications, systematization, Clavien-Dindo classification, OETA, URP, HoLEP, morbidity, prostate hyperplasia.

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УНИФИЦИРОВАННЫЕ КРИТЕРИИ ПОСЛЕОПЕРАЦИОННЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДОБРОКАЧЕСТВЕННОЙ ГИПЕРПЛАЗИИ ПРЕДСТАТЕЛЬНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Унификация критериев послеоперационных осложнений хирургических методов лечения доброкачественной гиперплазии предстательной железы (ДГПЖ) на основе классификации Clavien-Dindo и оценка эффективности и безопасности различных хирургических методов лечения ДГПЖ путем систематизации послеоперационных осложнений. 150 пациентов с ДГПЖ были распределены на три группы в зависимости от метода хирургического лечения гиперплазии простаты. I группу составили 60 (40%) больных, которым была выполнена открытая чреспузырная аденомэктомия простаты (ОАЭП), II - 50 (33,3%) пациентов, перенесших трансуретральную резекцию простаты (ТУРП), III - 40 (26,7%) больных, которым была выполнена гольмиевая лазерная энуклеация простаты (HoLEP). Использована классификация Clavien-Dindo для адаптации к оценке послеоперационных осложнений хирургического лечения ДГПЖ. Для объективной оценки качества хирургических вмешательств и систематизации осложнений с помощью классификации Clavien-Dindo, предварительно её необходимо адаптировать, с учетом специфики метода и послеоперационного периода. ОАЭП является эффективным методом устранения ИВО, но сопровождается более длительным периодом госпитализации по сравнению с ТУРП и HoLEP, более тяжелыми осложнениями, достоверно чаще требующими дополнительных вмешательств. По травматичности, частоте переливания крови и продолжительности пребывания пациентов в стационаре результаты ТУРП сопоставима с HoLEP, но уступает по частоте отдаленных осложнений.

Ключевые слова: ДГПЖ, осложнения, систематизация, классификация Clavien-Dindo, ОЭТА, TURP, HoLEP, заболеваемость, гиперплазия предстательной железы.

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BEZARAR PROSTATA BEZI GIPERPLAZIYASINI DAVOLASH JARROHLIK USULLARINING SAMARALI VA XAVFSIZLIGINI BAHOLASHDA OPERATSIYADAN KEYINGI ASORATLARNING BIRXILLASHTIRILGAN MEZONLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Clavien-Dindo tasnifi asosida bezarar prostata bezining iperplaziyasini (BPBG) davolashning jarrohlik usullarining operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlari mezonlarini birxillashtirish va operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarni tizimlashtirish orqali BPBGni davolashning turli jarrohlik usullarining samaradorligi va xavfsizligini baholash. BPBG bo'lgan 150 nafar bemor prostata bezi giperplaziyasini jarrohlik davolash usuliga qarab uch guruhga bo'lingan. I guruhga ochiq transvezikal prostata adenomektomiyasi (OTPA) qilingan 60 (40%) bemorlar, II - prostata bezining transuretral rezektsiyasi (PBTR) qilingan 50 (33,3%) bemorlar, III - prostata bezining golmiy lazer enukleatsiyasi (HoLEP) o'tkazilgan 40 (26,7%) bemorlar kirgan. Clavien-Dindo tasnifi BPBGni jarrohlik davolashning operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarni baholashga moslashish uchun ishlatilgan. Jarrohlikning sifatini ob'ektiv baholash va Clavien-Dindo tasnifidan foydalangan holda asoratlarni tizimlashtirish uchun uni birinchi navbatda usulning o'ziga xosligini va operatsiyadan keyingi davrni hisobga olgan holda moslashtirish kerak. OTPA infravezikal obstruksiyasini yo'q qilishning samarali usuli hisoblanadi, ammo PBTR va HoLEP bilan solishtirganda uzoqroq kasalxonaga yotqizish davri,

og'irroq asoratlar, sezilarli darajada tez-tez qo'shimcha jarrohliklarni talab qiladi. Travma, qon quyish chastotasi va bemorlarning kasalxonada qolish muddati nuqtai nazaridan TURP natijalari HoLEP natijalari bilan taqqoslanadi, ammo uzoq muddatli asoratlarning chastotasi bo'yicha pastroq.

Kalit so'zlar: BPBG, asoratlar, tizimlashtirish, Clavien-Dindo tasnifi, OETA, TURP, HoLEP, kasallik, prostata giperplaziyasi.

Relevance.

Currently, for the operative therapy of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), a lot of different surgical treatment methods have been proposed. Their number is growing from year to year [1].

Since the beginning of the 20th century, open endoscopic transurethral adenomectomy (OETA) was the only effective treatment method for BPH for a long time. Transvesical open adenomectomy was first performed in 1894 by J. Fuller and became widespread after the publication of the works of Peter Freyer (1900) [2]. According to the 2020 European Association of Urology (EAU) Guidelines, open adenomectomy is the most invasive and, at the same time, the most effective method of treating BPH with a long-term effect.

After the introduction of endoscopic transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP), this method has remained the gold standard for the surgical treatment of BPH for the past 40 years. It significantly improves the quality of urination and the patient's life [3]. However, TURP can also be accompanied by various complications, the most formidable of which are bleeding and transurethral resection syndrome (TUR-syndrome). The number and severity of these complications is directly dependent on the prostate volume, with an increase in which morbidity also increases.

The desire to create a method that combines the radical nature of OETA with the minimally invasive endourological interventions has led to emergence of various options for endoscopic enucleation of the prostate (EEP). In 1998, a fundamentally new HoLEP method (Holmium Laser Enucleation of the Prostate) appeared, which some authors call the new gold standard of BPH operative therapy [4,5].

Nevertheless, in a number of countries where medical centers do not have the necessary equipment or endourological techniques are at the development stage, open adenomectomy remains a popular method of BPH operative therapy. According to the 2021 EAU Guidelines [6], OETA should be offered to patients with a prostate volume > 80 ml and moderate to severe LUTS if bipolar transurethral enucleation of the prostate or HoLEP is not available. In addition, open surgery may be necessary in any urological center when BPH is combined with other urological pathology of the lower urinary tract, such as stones or bladder diverticulum [7,8].

High-tech minimally invasive endoscopic methods of surgical treatment of BPH are being actively introduced along with the traditional OETA in various state medical centers and private clinics of Uzbekistan in recent years. The simultaneous existence and use in practice of different methods of operative therapy indicates the complexity of the surgical method of treating this disease and also that its optimal variant has not yet been found. This in turn depends on many reasons, one of which is the lack of an objective assessment of the quality of surgical methods.

When performing both open and minimally invasive interventions in BPH, even qualified surgeons often experience mild and severe severity complications. All complications must be properly recorded and monitored. Therefore, it is important to introduce a unified system for assessing the quality of interferences, which should be accepted by the urological community.

The purpose of this study was to adapt the Clavien-Dindo classification by unifying the criteria for postoperative complications of different surgical treatments of BPH and to evaluate their efficacy and safety by systematizing postoperative complications.

Material and methods.

Case histories of 150 patients operated on for BPH were studied retro- and prospectively. All patients were divided into three groups depending on the operative therapy method for prostatic hyperplasia. Group 1 consisted of 60 (40%) patients who underwent OETA. Group 2 included 50 (33.3%) patients who underwent transurethral mono- (m-TURP) and bipolar electroresection of the

prostate (b-TURP). Group 3 consisted of 40 (26.7%) patients who underwent HoLEP (the period of mastering a new method).

Patients of Groups 1 and 2 were operated on in the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care (RSC EMC SB). Patients of group 3 were operated on in the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Urology in Tashkent (RSSPMCU). All operations were performed by qualified surgeons with many years of experience. HoLEP surgeries are the first results of the implementation phase of this method.

To systematize postoperative complications, we used the improved Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications. It was adapted for the operative therapy of BPH [9, 10]. It can be applied to various surgical treatment methods only after its adaptation, taking into account the method specifics.

Interference effectiveness was assessed based on IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score), QoL (Quality of Life), Qmax (maximum urine flow rate), Vpr. - the volume of the prostate; PVR (prostate residual volume), which were evaluated before and 1, 3, and 6 months after surgery. The American Society of Anesthesiologists' physical status classification system (ASA) was used for a correct assessment of the patient preoperative physical status [11].

Results.

As the first step to adapting the Clavien-Dindo classification, we considered it necessary to unify the criteria for an uncomplicated postoperative course of surgical treatment of BPH. In our opinion, these criteria will allow us to objectively evaluate the quality of any surgical treatment performed for BPH, both open and minimally invasive.

We have created criteria for an uncomplicated postoperative course based on many years of experience in our clinics in the treatment of BPH and post-operation patient management (Table 1).

Table 1.

Criteria for an uncomplicated postoperative course with operative therapy of BPH

1.	slight (non-intensive) urine staining with blood through the urethral catheter and/or cystostomy, which does not form blood clots with drainage dysfunction and require additional infusion (more than 1 liter), diuretic therapy and the prescription of hemostatic
2.	continuous drip lavage of the bladder up to 36 hours after surgery
3.	an increase in the patient's body temperature to 37.9 °C without chills for no more than 48 hours, not requiring antipyretic and infusion (more than 1 liter) therapy
4.	an intraoperatively installed hemostatic urethral catheter is in-line from 12 to 72 hours (as directed by the surgeon) without the development of an infectious and inflammatory process in the urinary tract (UT) and the need for additional interventions
5.	cystostomy drainage is in-line for up to 5 days after surgery
6.	transient bedwetting for up to 1 month in the absence of UT infection

Taking into account the criteria we created for the standard postoperative course of BPH operative therapy (Table 1), we determined the boundary where the normal uncomplicated course of the postoperative period turns into a complicated course and developed criteria for a complicated postoperative course. At the same time, we took into account the grade of severity and additional conservative and invasive interventions that required eradication, bringing it into line with the meaning of each of the five grades of the Clavien-Dindo classification (Table 2).

Table 2.

Criteria for postoperative complications in the BPH operative therapy for their systematization according to the Clavien-Dindo classification

Grade	Observable signs
I	- intense blood staining of urine coming through the urethral catheter and/or cystostomy, requiring constant bladder drip lavage, lasting more than 36 hours after surgery; - a hemostatic urethral catheter is in-line for more than 72 hours and/or the need for additional infusion and conservative therapy; - cystostomy drainage is in-line for more than five days, which required additional conservative therapy;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prolapse of the urethral hemostatic drainage, which required additional monitoring without invasive intervention; - violation of the function of the urethral and/or cystostomy drainage due to the formed blood clots and urine wetting around the drainage for up to 2 days; - one-day fever above 38°C or 37.0-38°C for more than 48 hours, requiring the prescription of antipyretic drugs or other additional therapy and infusion of more than 1 liter; - transient increase in the level of creatinine in the blood; - acute urinary retention (AUR) after removal of the drains, which required a single catheterization of the bladder; - treatment of postoperative wound infection; - urinary incontinence for more than one month, but not more than three months.
II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - infectious and inflammatory processes in the urinary tract, requiring additional antimicrobial (in addition to prophylactic) therapy (acute pyelonephritis, acute cystitis, acute prostatitis, acute urethritis, acute orchiepididymitis); - the need for analgesics for more than 72 hours after surgery or the prescription of narcotic analgesics due to undergone interference; - residual urine of more than 50 ml after removal of cystostomy and/or urethral drainage, requiring additional care and therapy, in addition to those indicated at grade I; - wetting with urine around the cystostomy drainage for more than 2 days, which requires an additional period of monitoring and administration of drugs, and suction-irrigation systems, in addition to those indicated for complications of the 1st grade; - any additional drug therapy as a result of an exacerbation of chronic concomitant pathology or developed after anesthesia (pneumonia, pleurisy, chronic bronchitis, intestinal paresis, indomitable vomiting, prolonged headache, etc.); - the need for parenteral nutrition; - the need to prescribe hemostatics; - the need for blood transfusion and blood substitutes; - urinary incontinence for more than three months.
IIIa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - repeated AUR that required recatheterization of the bladder; - a condition requiring therapeutic and diagnostic urethrocystoscopy; - replacement or re-insertion of a cystostomy or urethral drain, regardless of the problem cause (inadequate bladder drainage, drainage prolapse, urine leaking past the catheter, development of a urinoma); - intravesical obstruction due to blood clots, which required invasive intervention; - percutaneous (PC) cystostomy or recystostomy under local anesthesia; - any invasive interventions required in the postoperative period; - any diagnostic X-ray and radiological interventions in the postoperative period; - a patient with initially chronic renal failure in the intermittent stage. In the postoperative period, due to exacerbation of chronic renal failure - a forced session or sessions of hemodialysis.
IIIb	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bleeding from the adenoma bed or the bladder with the development of bladder tamponade, cleaning the bladder from bundles during general anesthesia (intraspinal anesthesia (SA), endotracheal anesthesia, combined); - retamponade of the adenoma bed; - PC cystostomy or recystostomy under general anesthesia; - open interventions (for postoperative urethral structure); - any other endoscopic interventions on general anesthesia for residual tissue, urethral stricture, bladder neck sclerosis (SSC).
IVa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - insufficiency of the function of one organ that developed after the intervention (kidneys, lungs, liver, heart (heart attack), central nervous system (stroke)) - requiring the patient to be in the intensive care unit; - injury of a neighboring organ, diagnosed in the postoperative period; - conducting a session of hemodialysis in a patient with an initially normal level of creatinine, due to developed renal failure; - sepsis.
IVb	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sepsis; septic shock; refractory shock (multiple organ failure), DIC syndrome and treatment in the intensive care unit
V	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - patient's death

In our opinion, the most difficult is to assess the lungs in grades I and II of complications and distinguish them, based on the increase in their severity. For this reason, the unification of the criteria for an uncomplicated postoperative course plays an important role in distinguishing relatively mild complications, which in practice are eliminated conservatively.

Analysis of the results of treatment of the Group 1 patients operated by the OETA method showed the largest number of complications 154 (256.6%), which were noted in the systematization of postoperative complications in 60 patients. At the same time, according to the adapted Clavien-Dindo classification, complications were divided as follows: grade I - 89 (57.8%), grade II - 48 (31.2%), grade IIIa - 9 (5.8%), grade IIIb - 3 (1.95%), grade IVa - 3 (1.95%), grade IVb - 0, grade V - 2 (1.3%). The effectiveness of OETA is shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

**Treatment effectiveness of patients with BPH undergone
OETA procedure, n=58**

№	Indicator	Before surgery	1 month after surgery	3 months after surgery	6 months after surgery
1.	IPSS	28.3 ± 0.3	7.5 ± 0.1*	6.6 ± 0.2*	5.7 ± 0.1*
2.	QoL	4.75 ± 0.1	3.05 ± 0.05*	2.1 ± 0.04*	1.9 ± 0.05*
3.	Qmax	6.6 ± 0.3	19.8 ± 0.2*	20.4 ± 0.3*	21.3 ± 0.3*
4.	Vpr.	90.4 ± 3.1	27.4 ± 0.7*	25.7 ± 0.7*	24.6 ± 0.6*
5.	PVR	246.2 ± 28.9	23.9 ± 2.2*	20.2 ± 1.7*	15.0 ± 1.45*

*P <0,05 compared with the preoperative period.

Of all complications, 137 (89%) were relatively mild and were eliminated conservatively. Additional invasive interventions were required to eliminate 12 (7.8%) complications. Five patients needed to be in the intensive care unit. Mortality was 1.3% (2) - 1 patient died due to cardiovascular insufficiency and one patient due to an acute cerebrovascular accident.

Analysis of the treatment results of Group 2 patients showed that the frequency of complications between m-TURP and b-TURP did not differ statistically; for this reason, we consider them together. Among the 50 patients who underwent TURP, 41 (82.0%) complications were observed in 28 (56%) patients. According to the adapted Clavien-Dindo classification, the complications were systematized: grade I - 16 (39%), grade II - 17 (41.5%), grade IIIa - 1 (2.4%), grade IIIb - 7 (17.1%). Complications of grades IVa, IVb, and V were noted.

The effectiveness of TURP is presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

**Treatment effectiveness of patients with BPH undergone
TURP procedure, n=50**

№	Indicator	Before surgery	1 month after surgery	3 months after surgery	6 months after surgery
1.	IPSS	25,1±0,5	10,6±0,35*	7,8±0,1*	6,2±0,2*
2.	QoL	4,6±0,1	3,98±0,1*	3,1±0,05*	2,1±0,04*
3.	Qmax	6,9±0,3	17,9±0,2*	19,5±0,2*	20,3±0,2*
4.	Vpr.	72,7±3,0	30,0±0,8*	28,1±0,7*	26,7±0,6*
5.	PVR	203,3±37,7	28,2±2,65*	22,3±1,7*	17,9±1,4*

*P <0,05 compared with the preoperative period.

Among all postoperative complications of TURP 33 (80.5%) were relatively mild and were eliminated conservatively. Invasive interventions were required to eliminate 8 (19.5%) complications. 7 (17.1%) of them were performed under general anesthesia.

Postoperative period analysis of the third group of patients who underwent HoLEP showed 28 (70%) complications in 20 patients (50%). At the same time, there were 8 (28.6%) cases of complications of grade I, grade II - 16 (57.1%), grade IIIa - 3 (10.7%), grade IIIb - 1 (3.6%). There were no complications of grade IVa, IVb and V. Of all the complications, 24 (85.7%) were relatively mild and were eliminated conservatively. Invasive interventions were required to eliminate 4 (14.3%) complications, one of them under general anesthesia.

The effectiveness of the operative therapy performed by the HoLEP method is presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

**Treatment effectiveness of patients with BPH undergone
HoLEP procedure, n=40**

№	Indicator	Before surgery	1 month after surgery	3 months after surgery	6 months after surgery
1.	IPSS	24.7 ± 0.6	7.6 ± 0.2*	6.8 ± 0.2*	5.9 ± 0.2*
2.	QoL	4.5 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.06*	2.3 ± 0.08*	2.0 ± 0.06*
3.	Qmax	10.7 ± 1.1	18.9 ± 0.3*	20.05 ± 0.4*	20.9 ± 0.3*
4.	Vпр.	91.0 ± 3.8	28.1 ± 1.0*	26.2 ± 1.0*	25.4 ± 0.9*
5.	PVR	77.2 ± 15.8	26.4 ± 3.1*	21.0 ± 3.3 *	17.1 ± 2.3*

*P <0,05 compared with the preoperative period.

Postoperative bleeding was observed in 37 (24.7%) patients among all groups. Blood transfusion was required in 7 patients: after HoLEP - 1 (2.5%), after TURP - 2 (4.0%), after OETA - 4 (6.7%) patients. The average postoperative bed-day after HoLEP was 3.8±0.2, after TURP - 3.3±0.2; after OETA - 8.6±0.3 days.

A detailed analysis of complications showed that there were 7 long-term complications, 2 (4.0%) posterior urethral strictures and 2 (4.0%) bladder neck strictures developed after TURP; 2 (3.3%) urethral strictures and 1 (1.7%) bladder neck sclerosis after OETA. Thus, fibrosclerotic processes in the urethra and bladder neck after HoLEP were not observed in the long-term postoperative period. Additional surgical interventions for long-term complications were not performed.

Discussion.

After the publication of work on the systematization of complications the Clavien-Dindo classification has also been used in urology to assess postoperative complications. In recent years it has become popular due to its universality. The reason for this is that the systematization of complications objectively shows the advantages of one method and the disadvantages of another. It also allows you to compare the quality of interventions of different surgeons, the results and effectiveness of treatment in different medical centers.

There are data on the use of a classification system to assess postoperative complications of radical retropubic, laparoscopic and robot-assisted prostatectomy [12,13,14], radical cystectomy [15,16], and renal surgery [17,18]. In 2019, Sagen E. et al. [19], and in 2020 Mbaeri T. et al. [20] applied a classification system to assess the complications of TURP. In 2020, Yalçın S. et al. published data on the use of the Clavien system to assess complications of HoLEP [21].

We must clearly distinguish between the normal and complicated course of the postoperative period to assess the nature of complications and divide their severity according to the logic proposed by the authors of the classification. In the literature available regarding the surgical treatment of BPH, we did not find an analysis of this problem which would indicate the criteria for a normal and complicated course of the postoperative period in the treatment of BPH. Previously, the standard course criteria of the postoperative period to the endoscopic treatment of nephrolithiasis were determined by the RSSPMCU team [22, 23]. Several authors who used the Clavien-Dindo classification to assess postoperative complications in the BPH treatment did not focus on this problem [18-21, 24]. As a result, due to the lack of criteria for a standard postoperative course in the surgical treatment of BPH, the authors systematized complications in different centers in their way. Some researchers considered some mild complications as a complication according to the logic of classification, while others considered similar changes in the postoperative period as a normal postoperative course. Therefore, a comparison of treatment results in one center is correct, but between centers, it is not.

We consider that the surgical treatment of BPH, regardless of the method, pursues a single ultimate goal - to deliver the patient of infravesicular obstruction by eliminating BPH. Therefore, the treatment results should be evaluated by a unified system for assessing the quality of interventions, regardless of which method or volume of intervention the goal was achieved.

Comparison of complications obtained after systematization with literature data, where complications are given without systematization, is not always correct since the detection of complications is always greater with systematization. According to Rassweiler J. et al. [25] as the technological and instrumental support of transurethral resection improved, the need for blood transfusion decreased to 0.4% against the previous 7.1% (our figure was 4%). The rate of TUR-syndrome was almost 0 (previously 1.1%) (we have 0), clot obstruction was 2% (previously 5%) (we have 6%), urinary tract infection was 1.7% (8.2%), (we have 8%). Urinary retention was 3% against the previous 9% (we have 4%). Long-term complications include strictures of the urethra (2.2-9.8%) (we have 4%), sclerosis of the bladder neck (0.3-9.2%) (we have 4%). Mortality after TURP was 0.0-0.025% (we have 0).

The following features were found when comparing TURP and HoLEP methods in a meta-analysis by Ahyai S.A. et al. [26]: blood transfusion was required in none of the cases, when performing HoLEP, while after TURP, its rate was 2.2% (our figures 4% and 2.5%); catheterization time after HoLEP ranged from 17.7 to 31 h, and after TURP from 43.4 to 57.8 h (we also have less than three days after both methods); The duration of hospitalization after laser enucleation averaged 2-3 days, and after TURP - 3-6 days [27], this indicator among our patients was 4.95 and 4.0.

OETA is characterized by high morbidity and a large number of postoperative complications. The mortality rate for European countries is about 0.25%. The overall complication percentage in the late 90s ranged from 12.5 to 23.02%. It was 17.3% by the second decade of the 21st century [5, 28-31]. Mortality rate in the OETA group in our study was 1.3% (2).

It should be emphasized that our analysis of the treatment effectiveness with all three surgery methods based on IPSS, QoL, Qmax, Vpr. and PVR (Tables 3, 4, 5) showed that all indicators were significantly different compared to baseline parameters and all methods of surgical treatment could be regarded as effective, with a relative difference in the timing of improvements in IPSS scores and the patient quality of life. So, after TURP, such an improvement occurred 1-2 months later. It was possible to reveal the real picture of the characteristics of the postoperative period of each treatment method only after the systematization of postoperative complications.

Conclusions.

1. It is possible to adapt the Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications in relation to the surgical removal of BPH by unifying the criteria for an uncomplicated postoperative course of BPH operative therapy.

2. TURP and HoLEP turned out to be less traumatic, after which the frequency and severity of complications according to the systematization was significantly lower (82.0% and 70.0%) compared with OETA (256.6%), $p < 0.01$. Rehabilitation of patients after TURP and HoLEP occurred earlier due to significantly early removal of urinary catheters (2.9 ± 0.1 and 2.2 ± 0.1 days) compared with OETA (8.4 ± 0.3 days, $p < 0.01$), hospital stay was statistically significantly reduced 3.3 ± 0.2 and 3.8 ± 0.2 days compared with OETA 8.6 ± 0.3 days ($p < 0.05$).

3. The cost-effectiveness was higher with TURP than with OETA, and with HoLEP it was higher than with TURP due to the absence of late complications in the form of urethral stricture and cicatricial deformity of the bladder neck. It was higher than with OETA due to the absence of late complications and mortality.

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